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Defensin beta 124 is repressed in luminal A breast cancer, and a position residing within the sequences encoding the defb124 gene is differentially hypermethylated.

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We recently demonstrated differential methylation of beta defensin genes in HER2+ breast cancer. We describe here transcriptional repression of defensin beta 124 in luminal A subtype breast cancer. In the tumor genome, a position residing within the defb124 gene was among those most differentially methylated genome-wide. The data support a role for defensin repression by epigenetic mechanisms in human cancer.